

OBTAINING ESSENTIAL OILS BY HOT EXTRACTION

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Abstract: Analysis of the physical properties of geranium oils manufactured at the factory revealed small deviations from the norm, which could be either the result of mixing oils of several types of geranium (i.e., in this way the manufacturer reduced the cost of oils), or the result of falsification. This analysis showed that the iodine numbers of geranium oils are slightly above the normal limits, therefore, the oils are less stable and more volatile, respectively, their quality decreases. This indicator may change as a result of the addition of various additives that affect the intensity of the aroma or as a result of mixing several types of oils.

Keywords: extractant, geranium, ether, unsaturation, iodine number, extraction

ПОЛУЧЕНИЕ ЭФИРНЫХ МАСЕЛ МЕТОДОМ ГОРЯЧЕЙ ЭКСТРАКЦИИ

Аннотация. Анализ физических свойств гераниевых масел, изготовленных на заводе, выявил небольшие отклонения от нормы, которые могли быть либо результатом смешивания масел нескольких видов герани (т.е. таким образом производитель удешевил масла), или результат фальсификации. Этот анализ показал, что йодные числа гераниевых масел несколько превышают нормальные пределы, следовательно, масла менее стабильны и более летучи, соответственно снижается их качество. Этот показатель может измениться в результате добавления различных добавок, влияющих на интенсивность аромата или в результате смешивания нескольких видов масел.

Ключевые слова: экстрагент, герань, эфир, ненасыщенность, йодное число, экстракция.

ESENTIAL MOYLARNI ISSIQ EKSTRAKSIYA YO'LI BILAN OLISH

Annotatsiya. Zavodda ishlab chiqarilgan geranium moylarining fizik xususiyatlarini tahlil qilish me'yordan kichik og'ishlarni aniqladi, bu bir necha turdagi geranium moylarini aralashtirish natijasi bo'lishi mumkin (ya'ni, ishlab chiqaruvchi shu tarzda moylarning narxini pasaytirgan), yoki qalbakilashtirish natijasi. Ushbu tahlil shuni ko'rsatdiki, geranium moylarining yod miqdori me'yordan biroz yuqoriroq, shuning uchun moylar kamroq barqaror va uchuvchan bo'lib, ularning sifati pasayadi. Bu ko'rsatkich aromaning intensivligiga ta'sir qiluvchi turli xil qo'shimchalar qo'shilishi yoki bir necha turdagi yog'larni aralashtirish natijasida o'zgarishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: ekstragent, geranium, efir, to'yinmaganlik, yod soni, ekstraktsiya

INTRODUCTION.

Even before the development of physico-chemical methods of analysis and before the development of chemistry in total, people noticed that plants have different properties, after exposure, for example,

with lavender, they feel peace, after a walk in orange orchards – on the contrary, cheerfulness. Also, the fact that such plants often have a spicy smell was not ignored, people began to try to extract this fragrance from such plants. When they succeeded, the oily liquid with a spicy smell was called essential oils [7]. With the development of analysis methods, it became known that essential oils are only a collective name, since each of these "oils" in its composition had many components, both organic and non-organic.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK.

The method is based on the ability of the extractant to absorb mixtures of organic substances that make up essential oils (terpenes and its derivatives) (Appendix 2). As a raw material for extraction, we took plant flowers, which are the raw materials for some essential oils popular in aromatherapy. All of them were dried: sisyphus, osmanthus, jasmine, rose, orange blossoms, lavender, mint, chrysanthemum, cornflower. As a solvent (extractant), first-pressed olive oil was used, which does not have an intrusive strong smell. Before the extraction, the iodine number was determined by reverse titration, for subsequent analysis of the effectiveness of this method based on changes in the indicator before and after extraction. The iodine number is an indicator of the unsaturation of the oil, for each type of oil, during extraction, the oil is saturated with various components, including unsaturated ones. Consequently, the indicator of the iodine number will change as it is extracted. If we compare the difference between the indicator before the extraction and after it with the literature data, we can calculate what percentage of unsaturated substances from the possible was extracted and thus reveal the efficiency of extraction [16, 21].

The dried raw materials were crushed in a mortar to increase the contact area with the solvent. Then, the raw materials were laid out in a thin layer in a container with a flat wide bottom, previously covered with gauze. They were filled with oil until the formation of a "mirror".

In a warm place (the temperature is constant about 37–40°C), the oil was infused for a month with tightly closed lids. Periodically replacing raw materials: oil was taken once a week, the raw materials were extracted, squeezed, then a new portion was laid. After the expiration of the period, the raw materials were extracted, the finished product was filtered by decantation [4]. For testing, two varieties of purchased geranium oils obtained from different varieties of this species were also taken.

Table 1

Physical indicators of essential oils

Plant oil	Refractive indices and density experience	Refractive indices and densities literature data
Common geranium	Density =0.900 Refractive index = 1.483	Density = 0.886-0.898 Refractive index in 20C 1.464-1.472
Rose	Density =0,848 Refractive index = 1.450	Density in 20 C 0.8560.870 Refractive index in 20C 1.453-1.464 Geranium

Geranium rosacea	Density =0,909 Refractive index = 1.475	Density 0.894-0.905 1.467-1.473
Ziziphora	Density =0,835 Refractive index = 1.467	
Lavender	Density =0.875 Refractive index = 1.460	Density in 20C 0.8760.892 Refractive index in 20C 1.475-1.464
Osmanthus	Density =0.902 Refractive index = 1.500	Density in 20C 0.910- 0.923 Refractive index in 20C 1.509
Mint	Density =0,897 Refractive index = 1.459	Density = 0.901-0.912 Refractive index in 20C 1.460-1.463
Chrysanthemum	Density =0,901 Refractive index = 1.469	
Jasmine	Density = 0,925 Refractive index = 1.470	Density in 20C 0.935- 0.948 Refractive index in 20C Density =1.485- 1.491
Cornflower	Density = 0,980 Refractive index = 1.549	Density in 0,985-0,990 Refractive index in 1,5521,560

As physical characteristics, we took the following: density, refractive index, organoleptic indicators: color, smell, taste.

1. Oil obtained from geranium rosacea flowers: light brown, translucent, with a bright characteristic smell, bitter taste.
2. Oil obtained from ordinary geranium flowers: brown, translucent, with a bright smell, bitter taste.
3. Oil obtained from the flowers of ziziphora: golden brown, translucent, with a slightly pronounced, sweet smell, bitter taste.
4. Oil obtained from osmanthus flowers: light brown, translucent, with a weakly pronounced heavy odor, bitter taste.
5. Oil obtained from orange tree flowers: yellowish-brown, translucent, with a pronounced citrus smell, bitter.
6. Oil obtained from lavender flowers: golden, transparent, with a pronounced specific smell, bitter.
7. Oil obtained from jasmine flowers: golden, transparent, with a delicate, sweet smell, bitter.
8. Oil obtained from cornflower flowers: brown, translucent, with a faint odor, bitter.
9. Oil obtained from rose flowers: light brown, translucent, with a bright, heavy smell, bitter.
10. Oil obtained from mint leaves: golden brown, translucent, with a pronounced specific smell.

Determination of chemical parameters of essential oils. As chemical characteristics of essential oils, we took the following: iodine number, saponification number, acid number, essential number.

The acid number is measured by the number of milligrams of potassium hydroxide, which is necessary to neutralize the free fatty acids contained in 1 g of fat. The acid number is a characteristic of the quality of the oil. For each of the oils there is a certain indicator, the norms of the content of free acids. If the content of these components is lower, therefore the oil is of poor quality, and if the indicator is exceeded, therefore we can talk about the non-natural origin of the oil.

Saponification number is the number of milligrams of KOH required to neutralize both free and bound (in the form of glycerides) fatty acids contained in 1 g of oil. The content of free fatty acids in the oil is characterized by an acid number, and the content of acid esters bound in the oil is characterized by an essential number, i.e. the number of milligrams of hydroxide dripping necessary to neutralize the fatty acids released during saponification of essential bonds in 1 g of oil. The experimental ether number is determined by the difference between the saponification number and the acid number. We determined the saponification number according to the methodology in the appendix. Next, the essential number for these oils was calculated by the difference between the saponification number and the acid number.

The iodine number is expressed by the number of grams of iodine needed to saturate the unsaturated fatty acids contained in 100 g of fat. The iodine number is one of the most important indicators for oils (fats). One thing allows us to judge the degree of saturation of oil (fat), their volatility, tendency to rancidity and other changes that occur during the storage and processing of essential oils. The more unsaturated fatty acids are contained in fat, the higher the iodine number. The decrease in the iodine number during the storage of oil is an indicator of its deterioration. The iodine number was determined according to the method in the appendix. The principle of the method is based on the property of unsaturated fatty acids to attach halogens at the place of double bonds. Unreacted iodine is titrated with 0.1 N sodium thiosulfate solution.

We have obtained the results presented in Table 2 and Table 3

Table 2

Chemical parameters of geranium essential oils

Oil	Acid Number Practice	Acid Number Theor.	The Ethereal Number. Practice	The Ethereal Number. Theor.	Iodine number Practice.	Iodine number Theor.	Saponification number Practice	Saponification number Theor.
Common Geranium	7,5	5-9	88	32-70	139	130	310	220
Geranium rosacea	6	2-5	91	39-72	138	128	331	245

Table3
The ration of iodine numbers before and after extraction

Oil	Iodine number after extraction – 90*	Iodine number according to literature data	% extractions
Roses	44	133	33
Ziziphoras	9.6	120	8
Lavender	46	135	34
Osmanthus	43.5	128	34
Mints	40	133	30
Chrysanthemums	34.3	127	27
Jasmine	16	123	13
Cornflower	22	125	18

The indicators of purchased geranium rosacea and geranium vulgaris do not correspond to the indicators provided by the literary source, namely: the saponification number and the essential number are greatly overestimated, respectively, most likely these oils were falsified "for geranium" for a more intense aroma, by adding synthetic citranellol, geraniol, terpineol and D.R. The iodine number indicator is slightly above the limits norms [22].

CONCLUSION.

We have implemented a physico-chemical analysis of essential oils to establish their quality. We conducted an organoleptic analysis, as a result, no deviations were detected. Analysis of the physical properties of geranium oils manufactured at the factory revealed small deviations from the norm, which could be either the result of mixing oils of several types of geranium (i.e., in this way the manufacturer reduced the cost of oils), or the result of falsification.

When determining the indicators of the iodine number of oils, we found out that the highest recovery rate was for rose, lavender and osmanthus oils. The indicators of chrysanthemum and ziziphora were the lowest. At the same time, the results of no plant species were close to 100%.

This analysis showed that the iodine numbers of geranium oils are slightly above the normal limits, therefore, the oils are less stable and more volatile, respectively, their quality decreases. This indicator may change as a result of the addition of various additives that affect the intensity of the aroma or as a result of mixing several types of oils.

The saponification number and the essential number for these oils were 2 times higher than normal, which indicates the unnatural origin of these oils, contrary to the manufacturer's statement. This indicator characterizes the phytoncidal properties of oils, the brightness of the aroma, therefore, are the most important in essential oils.

On the one hand, it can be argued that with such indicators, the quality of essential oils should increase, however, due to the complexity of extracting oils from plants, natural oils have a higher cost

than synthetic ones, so the manufacturer saves on production and adds various synthetic substances that can cause allergies or poisoning, since it does not indicate the presence of additives on the packaging.

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